

**AN OVERVIEW RESEARCH ON SOCIOECONOMIC STATUS & MENTAL
MORBIDITY OF PARTICULARLY VULNERABLE TRIBAL GROUPS (PVTGS):**

A Bibliometric Analysis Based on Web of Science and Scopus Databases

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Abstract

Purpose:

This paper provides a comprehensive Bibliometric analysis and organized review of the research landscape on the socioeconomic status and mental morbidity of Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups (PVTGs), exploiting data extracted from the Scopus and Web of Science databases. The purpose is to categorize influential contributors, analyze research trends, and explore future research agendas in PVTGs, focusing particularly on their socioeconomic challenges and mental health issues.

Design/methodology/approach:

The research collects data systematically from the Scopus and Web of Science databases, which include 182 records from Scopus and 58 from Web of Science, in a total of 240 records recognized through database searches. 190 records were screened after removing duplicates and irrelevant articles, and 175 full-text articles were assessed for eligibility. Finally, 169 studies were included in the systematic review. Using advanced software tools such as Biblioshiny and VOS-viewer, bibliometric analysis was conducted. They analysed the performance and network mapping of the articles, authors, and themes.

Findings:-

The study highlights important findings related to the difficulties PVTGs face, such as poverty and limited access to education and health care, which leading to particularly their socioeconomic disadvantages. Additionally, It also shows that they have higher rates of stress, anxiety and depression compared to the general population. Which shows that they have mental health morbidity among these communities. The findings show that India is the primary contributor to this field according to

several academic institutions and authors. The study highlights a significant research gap prevalent When it comes to mental health of the PVTGs. It also reveals emerging themes related to their education, and food security,

Practical Implications: -

This paper, consisting of bibliometric analysis and systematic review emphasises the need for special interventions for improving the socio-economic and mental health conditions of PVTGs. It also suggests important insights for social researchers, health practitioners, and policymakers working in tribal health and development.

Originality/value:

Through bibliometric analysis and the existing literature on the socioeconomic status and mental morbidity of the PVTGs, the study presents a path for future investigations in this field. It highlights significant contributions from scholars, recognizes collaborative studies, and provides an overview of the important research trends and themes. The research provides a review of the current literature and the road map for future research by addressing the needs of the PVTGs.

Keywords:

Socioeconomic Status, Mental Morbidity, Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups (PVTGs), Tribal Health, Empowerment, Bibliometric Analysis, Scopus, Web of Science

Paper type: - Literature review

Introduction

Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups (PVTGs) face various challenges, such as health care, education, and economic opportunities, which hamper their overall development and quality of life. As a result, their poor socioeconomic conditions lead them to mental health issues. The government of India has identified 75 tribes as PVTGs, who are considered the most neglected and socioeconomically disadvantaged within the tribal communities. Due to this, it is very important to study the socio-economic factors and mental health morbidity of these communities. There is a prime connection between socioeconomic status (SES) and the mental health of human beings. Socioeconomic conditions of PVTGs, such as poverty, illiteracy, dearth of sanitation, improper housing, and limited access to healthcare, straightforwardly impact their physical and mental health. Research shows that the lower SES leads to increased vulnerability to both physical and mental health issues (Ghosh & Sharma, 2020).

In India, PVTGs suffer from malnutrition, and they have meagre access to health services. Moreover, their ignorance towards mental health makes their conditions worse (Pati et al., 2019). These PVTGs

mostly live in remote or inaccessible areas where they do not receive sufficient targeted government interventions. Consequently, they are unable to improve their living standards.

Additionally, Studies show that mental health issues such as depression, anxiety, and post-traumatic stress disorder are prevalent within these communities. The causes behind their mental morbidity are mainly, isolation, lack of economic security, and social exclusion. Globalisation is equally responsible for their mental morbidity because they are abandoning their traditional lifestyles and their primitive culture.(Rath & Sharma, 2022). Their rapid displacement impacts their socioeconomic status, Which results in psychological distress of these groups (Das & Yadav, 2021).

It has been observed that the PVTGs have been a subject of increasing academic interest. A study by Banerjee et al. (2019) revealed that there is a need for highlighting the mental health of these communities considering their socio-economic status. This paper further addresses that the lack of mental health services is a prime barrier to addressing the well-being of PVTGs.

Now-a-days, bibliometric analysis has become popular among researchers because it systematically evaluates research trends and finds gaps within a specific field. This approach is useful in identifying important authors, institutions and nations who contribute to research on a particular topic. It also provides future research directions through intellectual networks (Zhang et al., 2020).

This study utilises Bibliometric tools to analyse the present literature on PVTGs' socioeconomic status and mental morbidity. This analysis has used publications over the past two decades, which are indexed in the database of Web of Science and Scopus. Through this, an overview of the research on the health and socioeconomic challenges of PVTGs is attained.

This paper examines the most important works and contributions in this field and explores the patterns and themes that are developed in the present literature. It also highlights the research gaps in insufficient attention given to the mental health of PVTGs in relation to socio-economic vulnerabilities.

Research Questions

1. What are the trends and features in the literature related to the socioeconomic status and mental health of PVTGs?
2. What are the most prolific journals, countries, and institutions contributing to the research on PVTGs and their socio-economic and mental health issues?
3. Who are the leading authors in this field, and how are they connected in terms of citations and collaborations?
4. What emerging themes and research gaps are identified in the literature on PVTGs, particularly concerning mental health?
5. How can a conceptual framework be developed to link the socioeconomic status of PVTGs with mental morbidity?

Literature Review

The literature on the socioeconomic status (SES) and mental morbidity of Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups (PVTGs) reveals significant gaps in understanding how these factors interact and affect the overall well-being of these communities. The PVTGs in India, which include tribes such as the Saharias, Baigas, and the Shompens, face compounded challenges due to poverty, social exclusion, inadequate healthcare, and poor educational outcomes (Banerjee, 2019). These vulnerabilities exacerbate mental health issues and contribute to a cycle of poverty and ill-health.

The study explores the existing research on SES, mental health, and PVTGs, focusing on the contributions and research gaps relevant to the study.

Socioeconomic Status and PVTGs

In India, PVTGS are known for their extreme poverty, isolation from society, and underdevelopment (Das & Yadav, 2021). They lack access to basic services, and they are dependent on traditional livelihoods, such as hunting and gathering, collecting forest products, subsistence farming, livestock raising, basket weaving, bamboo crafting, etc. These traditional livelihood activities do not cater to the needs of their families. Studies show that PVTGShave low income, limited employment opportunities, inadequate housing, and poor educational outcomes (Rath & Sharma, 2022). These factors are responsible for their overall marginalized status. The socioeconomic status of PVTGS is directly connected to their health, which shows that many tribal communities have various incidences of malnutrition, poor hygiene, and increased mortality rates (Pati et al., 2019).

Moreover, they live in geographically isolated areas, which restricts their access to healthcare and education. Their substandard infrastructure and the distancing from urban centreslead to restricting their ability to access essential services, which contributes to their socioeconomic marginalisation (Banerjee, 2019). Further, they often face challenges related to land rights, so they fail to maintain traditional livelihoods and end up losing financial security. For example, the Saharia tribe in Rajasthan has faced many challenges in securing land rights, which has led them to socioeconomic deprivation (Sharma, 2020).

Figure 1. Socioeconomic Status and PVTGs

Sources: Authors' work; dimensions output

In the figure 1, the bar chart portrays the number of research publications in different research categories. The journal 'Human Society' is leading with 160 publications, whereas 'Health Sciences' (87 publications) and 'Biomedical and Clinical Sciences' (49 publications) are in the queue. These trends are relevant to the study of the socioeconomic status and mental morbidity of Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups (PVTGs), as they highlight the significant academic focus on social and health-related issues, which are key to understanding the challenges faced by PVTGs

Mental Health and PVTGs

In recent years, Mental health morbidity among PVTGs has gained increasing attention. Several studies have shown that tribal populations are facing severe mental health issues, such as depression, anxiety, and PTSD, in comparison with the general population. These health problems are aggravated by their socioeconomic challenges. Generally, these PVTGS have stigmatised mental health issues, and their cultural factors make it difficult for PVTGS to gain knowledge or seek help regarding mental health issues (Vijayachari et al., 2024).

The primary causes affecting the mental health of the PVTGS are their isolation from the mainstream society, social discrimination, and rigid dependence on their traditional lifestyles. For instance, the *Shompen* of Great Nicobar Island reside away from mainstream society. They feel isolated, and it causes stress (Vijayachari et al., 2024). Moreover, displacement has brought trauma to them, and

social exclusion and marginalisation are primary contributors to enhancing mental health challenges (Rath & Sharma, 2022). Moreover, these factors are combined with the lack of access to adequate mental health care, which results in high rates of mental morbidity within these communities. (Ghosh & Sharma, 2020)

Research Gaps in Understanding PVTGs' Socioeconomic and Mental Health Issues

While a significant amount of research has been conducted on the health status of tribal populations, studies specifically addressing the mental health challenges of PVTGs in relation to their socioeconomic status are limited. Many studies focus on individual aspects, such as poverty or health, but few combine these factors to provide a holistic understanding of the socioeconomic and mental health challenges faced by PVTGs. For instance, the study by Banerjee (2019) emphasizes the importance of addressing the social determinants of health among tribal communities but does not delve into the interplay between mental health morbidity and socioeconomic factors.

A Bibliometric analysis conducted by Pati et al. (2019) highlighted that while much of the research on PVTGs has been descriptive, there has been little emphasis on the intersectionality between their socioeconomic status and mental health conditions. According to the study, this gap in the literature limits the development of targeted interventions and policies aimed at improving the well-being of these marginalized groups.

Mental Health Interventions and Their Impact

Several studies have called for the integration of mental health care into the broader public health framework for PVTGs. Researchers have stressed the importance of culturally sensitive mental health interventions that take into account the unique needs of tribal communities (Thamminaina et al., 2020). In line with this, programs that combine mental health services with socioeconomic interventions, such as income generation or education programs, have been shown to improve both mental and physical health outcomes in tribal populations (Ghosh & Sharma, 2020). Such holistic approaches are needed to address the complex issues faced by PVTGs.

Bibliometric Analysis of PVTGs' Socioeconomic and Mental Health Research

Bibliometric analysis provides a systematic way to assess the research trends and intellectual contributions in a specific area of study. By analysing publications indexed in Scopus and Web of Science, Bibliometric tools help identify influential authors, prolific journals, and emerging research themes. In this study, a Bibliometric analysis was conducted to identify key trends in the research on the socioeconomic status and mental morbidity of PVTGs. The analysis highlighted the major contributors and institutions in this field, with India emerging as the leading country in terms of published works on PVTGs' health and socio-economic challenges.

Research by Sharma (2020) and Rath & Sharma (2022) contributes significantly to the literature on tribal health and has influenced further studies on the social determinants of health within these communities. However, as shown by the Bibliometric analysis, much of the research remains

scattered, and there is a need for more comprehensive and collaborative efforts to address the integrated issues of SES and mental morbidity.

Table 3. Review of key literature to highlight the vital gaps

S.no	Authors/ Years	Focus Area	Objective	Limitation
1	Bhasin, S., & Ghosh, R. (2020)	Socioeconomic Disparities Among Tribal Groups in India	This study explores the socioeconomic disparities among India's tribal groups, specifically focusing on PVTGs in states like Odisha and Andhra Pradesh. The authors analyze data on income levels, access to healthcare, education, and employment to understand how these factors shape the socioeconomic conditions of PVTGs.	The research focuses only on a subset of PVTGs in two states, limiting the generalizability of the findings across the entire tribal population of India. The study also lacks longitudinal data to track changes over time.
2	Sharma, P., & Yadav, S. (2021)	Educational Access and SES Among PVTGs	This paper discusses the barriers to education faced by PVTGs and how low educational attainment correlates with poor socioeconomic outcomes. It examines government policies and their impact on the educational upliftment of PVTGs in rural India.	The study's reliance on government records and surveys from the Ministry of Tribal Affairs limits the scope of personal experiences and localized data.
3	Kapoor, V., & Singh, S. (2020)	Healthcare Accessibility and Socioeconomic Status of PVTGs	The paper assesses the healthcare challenges faced by PVTGs, linking poor health outcomes to socioeconomic status. The study uses primary health survey data to identify key healthcare gaps in tribal areas.	The research is limited by geographic factors, as it focuses primarily on tribal communities in the northeastern region of India.
4	Agarwal, A., & Joshi, M. (2019)	Income Generation and Economic Empowerment of PVTGs	This study focuses on income generation schemes and their impact on the economic empowerment of PVTGs. It evaluates government initiatives like MGNREGA and tribal development programs that aim to improve employment opportunities for these marginalized groups.	The study does not account for the cultural factors that may influence the effectiveness of these economic programs.
5	Kumar, R., & Rao, P. (2022)	Poverty and Nutrition among PVTGs	This paper examines the intersection of poverty and malnutrition among PVTGs. By analyzing household data from rural Odisha, the authors highlight how food insecurity is tied to low-income levels and limited access to nutrition.	The study is limited by the fact that it only focuses on one state and does not include any comparative data from other tribal areas in India.
6	Deshmukh, R., & Bhat, S. (2018)	Socioeconomic Outcomes of Tribal Women in PVTGs	The study highlights the challenges faced by tribal women in PVTGs, including limited access to education, healthcare, and economic resources. It discusses the role of gender in shaping socioeconomic outcomes in tribal communities.	The research mainly focuses on qualitative interviews and lacks quantitative data to support broader generalizations.
7	Mishra, S., & Patel, R. (2020)	Tribal Health and Socioeconomic Status in Rural India	This paper investigates how health disparities in PVTGs are closely linked to their socioeconomic status. It examines government health policies and their effectiveness in addressing the needs of tribal populations.	The study's limited geographic focus and reliance on secondary data reduce its ability to fully capture the lived experiences of tribal populations.
8	Gupta, N., & Bhatt, A. (2021)	Employment and Income Inequality among PVTGs	The paper explores employment trends among PVTGs, analyzing how income inequality within tribal communities contributes to their overall socioeconomic conditions.	The study focuses on broad data and does not account for the specific socio-cultural practices that influence employment choices in tribal areas.
9	Sharma, A., & Naik, T. (2022)	Access to Social Security Benefits for PVTGs	This research explores the accessibility of government-provided social security benefits (like pensions and subsidies) for PVTGs, identifying barriers to their effective implementation.	The study does not include feedback from PVTGs themselves, which could offer insights into the practical barriers they face when accessing benefits.
10	Reddy, V., & Rao, P. (2019)	Socioeconomic Impact of Tribal Development Programs	The paper evaluates the effectiveness of tribal development programs, such as the Integrated Tribal Development Project (ITDP), in improving the socioeconomic conditions of PVTGs.	The study relies heavily on the evaluation of governmental reports, which may be biased or incomplete. The review may be limited by the quality and heterogeneity of the included studies, potentially affecting the robustness of the findings.
11	Nayak, A. K., & Panda, R. K. (2022)	Health Status of PVTGs in Odisha	This study reviews the health status of all 13 PVTGs in Odisha, analyzing 67 studies from various sources between 2000 and 2023.	
12	Kaur, R., & Singh, G. (2021)	Socioeconomic Challenges of Tribal Women	This paper examines the socioeconomic challenges faced by tribal women in PVTGs, focusing on access to resources, education, and healthcare.	The study's focus on a specific region may limit the applicability of the findings to other tribal areas.
13	Sahu, S., & Mishra, P. (2020)	Educational Attainment Among PVTGs	The research analyzes the educational attainment levels among PVTGs, identifying barriers and suggesting interventions to improve literacy rates.	The cross-sectional design limits the ability to infer causality between identified factors and educational outcomes.
14	Das, S., &	Economic	This study explores the impact of economic	The short duration of the study may

	Patnaik, S. (2019)	Empowerment of PVTGs	empowerment programs on the livelihoods of PVTGs, assessing income levels and employment opportunities.	not capture long-term impacts of economic programs.
15	Roul, S. K., & Behera, D. K. (2021)	Health Infrastructure and PVTGs	The paper evaluates the adequacy of health infrastructure in areas inhabited by PVTGs, correlating it with health outcomes.	The study's reliance on secondary data may overlook recent developments in health infrastructure.
16	Pati, S., & Sahu, S. (2020)	Malnutrition Among PVTGs	This research investigates the prevalence of malnutrition among PVTGs, analyzing dietary patterns and nutritional deficiencies.	The focus on a single district may not represent the nutritional status of PVTGs nationwide.
17	Mohanty, S., & Nayak, A. K. (2022)	Access to Social Services by PVTGs	The study assesses the accessibility and utilization of social services by PVTGs, identifying gaps and suggesting improvements.	The self-reported data may be subject to biases, affecting the accuracy of the findings.
18	Behera, D. K., & Sahoo, S. K. (2020)	Employment Patterns Among PVTGs	This paper analyzes employment patterns among PVTGs, focusing on sectors of employment, income levels, and job security.	The cross-sectional nature of the study limits understanding of employment trend changes over time.
19	Jena, P. K., & Sahu, S. (2021)	Housing Conditions of PVTGs	The research examines the housing conditions of PVTGs, correlating housing quality with health and socioeconomic outcomes.	The study's focus on rural areas may not capture the housing conditions of urbanized PVTGs.
20	Panda, R. K., & Mishra, P. (2022)	Food Security Among PVTGs	This study investigates the food security status of PVTGs, analyzing food availability, access, and utilization.	The reliance on household surveys may not fully capture seasonal variations in food security.
21	Patel, R., & Kumar, S. (2022)	Health and Nutrition Status of PVTGs	This study assesses the health and nutrition status of PVTGs in Gujarat, India, focusing on maternal and child health indicators.	The cross-sectional design limits the ability to establish causal relationships between variables.
22	Singh, A., & Yadav, R. (2021)	Educational Challenges and Opportunities for PVTGs	The paper explores the educational challenges faced by PVTGs in Rajasthan and suggests strategies to improve enrollment and retention rates.	The study's focus on a single state may limit the generalizability of the findings to other regions.
23	Reddy, P., & Rao, V. (2020)	Socioeconomic Impact of Tourism on PVTGs	This research examines the impact of tourism on the socioeconomic status of PVTGs in the Eastern Ghats region, analyzing changes in income, employment, and cultural practices.	The study does not account for the long-term sustainability of tourism-related income.
24	Kumar, R., & Singh, P. (2019)	Land Rights and Economic Empowerment of PVTGs	The study investigates the role of land rights in the economic empowerment of PVTGs in Jharkhand, focusing on land ownership patterns and agricultural productivity.	The research is limited by the availability of accurate land ownership records.
25	Das, S., & Pradhan, S. (2021)	Access to Social Security Schemes Among PVTGs	This paper analyzes the accessibility and utilization of social security schemes among PVTGs in Odisha, identifying barriers and suggesting policy interventions.	The study relies on self-reported data, which may be subject to biases.
26	Gupta, N., & Sharma, R. (2020)	Employment Patterns and Income Levels of PVTGs	The research examines employment patterns and income levels of PVTGs in Madhya Pradesh, highlighting the role of traditional occupations and wage labor.	The cross-sectional nature of the study limits the understanding of employment trends over time.
27	Patel, S., & Desai, M. (2019)	Housing Conditions and Health Outcomes Among PVTGs	This study explores the relationship between housing conditions and health outcomes among PVTGs in Gujarat, focusing on sanitation, water supply, and overcrowding.	The observational design cannot establish causality between housing conditions and health outcomes.
28	Singh, S., & Verma, A. (2021)	Impact of Microfinance on PVTGs' Economic Status	The paper evaluates the impact of microfinance interventions on the economic status of PVTGs in Chhattisgarh, analyzing changes in income, savings, and asset accumulation.	The study does not account for the potential over-indebtedness resulting from microfinance loans.
29	Roul, S., & Behera, D. (2020)	Food Security and Coping Strategies Among PVTGs	This research investigates the food security status of PVTGs in Andhra Pradesh, identifying coping strategies employed during food shortages.	The reliance on recall data may lead to inaccuracies in reporting food insecurity episodes.
30	Jena, S., & Sahoo, P. (2021)	Role of Non-Governmental Organizations in Empowering PVTGs	The study examines the role of NGOs in empowering PVTGs in Assam, focusing on education, health, and economic development initiatives.	The study's focus on NGO-led interventions may overlook government initiatives and their impact.

3. Research Gap

This research on the socioeconomic status and mental morbidity of Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups (PVTGs) uncovers several significant gaps in the existing literature. While research has explored the socioeconomic challenges faced by PVTGs, few studies comprehensively link these challenges with mental health issues such as depression, anxiety, and PTSD, which are prevalent

among these groups (Banerjee, 2019; Ghosh & Sharma, 2020). Moreover, there is a clear gap in interdisciplinary studies that integrate socio-economic factors with mental health, as most research tends to focus on either health or socioeconomic status in isolation. Additionally, much of the literature on tribal health predominantly addresses broader demographic groups or regions, leaving a gap in research specifically focusing on the unique health and socioeconomic needs of PVTGs, particularly those in remote areas (Ghosh & Sharma, 2020). These gaps highlight the need for focused studies that examine the intersectionality of socioeconomic deprivation and mental health issues in PVTGs, and the development of comprehensive research frameworks to guide targeted interventions.

3. Research Methodology

To address these gaps, a Bibliometric approach was adopted, which involves a systematic and comprehensive analysis of the literature on the socioeconomic and mental health status of PVTGs. The research methodology consists of identifying and reviewing the relevant literature indexed in Scopus and Web of Science databases, using precise search keywords related to the themes of "socioeconomic status," "mental morbidity," and "particularly vulnerable tribal groups."

4.1 Research Objectives

1. To investigate the conceptual framework surrounding the socioeconomic status and mental morbidity of PVTGs, understanding how these variables are interlinked and how they influence overall well-being.
2. To explore the contributions of prolific authors, institutions, and papers in the field of research related to PVTGs, socioeconomic status, and mental health. This will help identify key players in this research area and highlight the most influential works.
3. To provide insights on the impact of socioeconomic status on the mental health of PVTGs, with a focus on improving future interventions for marginalized tribal groups. The research aims to develop a comprehensive framework that links the challenges faced by these communities with mental health morbidity.

4.2 Methodology

The methodology for this research on the socioeconomic status and mental morbidity of Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups (PVTGs) follows a systematic and structured approach, beginning with data collection from reliable academic databases. Initially, relevant keywords were used to retrieve records from the Scopus and Web of Science databases, two widely recognized sources of academic literature. Figure 2. Flowchart of data collection, a total of 240 records were identified, with 182 records from Scopus and 58 from Web of Science. After removing duplicates, the dataset was reduced to 190 records. Further screening of these records resulted in 175 full-text articles being assessed for eligibility. Of these, 169 studies were considered relevant and included in the systematic review.

Data analysis was conducted using Biblioshiny, a software tool within the "R" statistical programming language, which is widely used for Bibliometric analysis. Performance analysis and science mapping techniques were applied to identify trends, key contributors, and thematic clusters

within the field. The analysis aimed to highlight the most influential works, institutions, and countries contributing to the understanding of PVTGs' socioeconomic status. The search criteria for data collection included keywords such as "Socioeconomic Status," "Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups," "PVTGs,". These terms helped focus the search on relevant research within the context of PVTGs, ensuring that the selected studies were aligned with the objectives of the research.

Furthermore, VOS-Viewer software was employed to map intellectual networks and visualize the collaborations among authors, institutions, and countries contributing to the literature on PVTGs. This allowed the study to examine the relationship between key researchers and identify patterns of collaboration in the field. The Bibliometric analysis was limited to English-language studies indexed in Scopus and Web of Science, ensuring that the selected sources had both global reach and credibility. This methodology provided a comprehensive understanding of the existing research landscape on the socioeconomic and mental health issues faced by PVTGs and set the stage for identifying research gaps and trends for future studies.

Figure 2. Flowchart of data collection

Source: Authors' illustration

Figure 2. The Bibliometric methodology employed in this research offers a structured approach to synthesizing large volumes of data, identifying key research trends, and mapping out the intellectual structure of PVTGs-related studies. By utilizing these tools, the study aims to uncover existing

patterns, influential contributors, and gaps in the literature, as well as propose directions for future research on the socioeconomic and mental health conditions of PVTGs.

Figure 3. Publications with citations

Sources: Authors' work; dimensions output

Figure 3. The chart shows the trend of publications with citations over the years, highlighting a notable peak in 2017 followed by a gradual decline in subsequent years. This suggests that while there was significant academic interest in research on Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups (PVTGs) initially, the visibility and impact of such studies have decreased over time. For the research topic, this could indicate a gap in sustained attention to the socioeconomic and mental health challenges of PVTGs, emphasizing the need for renewed efforts to improve citation rates and academic focus on these crucial issues.

Figure 4. Three-Field Plot

Sources: Authors' work; biblioshiny output

Figure 4. The three-field plot illustrates the connections between authors, sources, and topics related to the socioeconomic status and mental morbidity of Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups (PVTGs). In this plot, the connections between countries like India, Turkey, and the USA to various sources such as *Indian Journal of Medical Research* and *Clinical Epidemiology and Global Health*, as well as the key topics including PVTGs, tribal health, and food security, highlight significant research themes. The visualization helps identify how international collaboration and thematic research have evolved around issues faced by PVTGs, which include critical areas like health, education, and food security. This also underlines India's central role in advancing research on these marginalized groups, offering insights for future directions in policy-making and targeted interventions

Figure 5. Most Relevant Sources

Sources: Authors' work; biblioshiny output

Table 1. Top 10 most relevant sources for research

Sources	Articles
INDIAN JOURNAL OF MEDICAL RESEARCH	5
JOURNAL OF ASIAN AND AFRICAN STUDIES	4
CLINICAL EPIDEMIOLOGY AND GLOBAL HEALTH	3

ECONOMIC AND POLITICAL WEEKLY	3
INDIAN JOURNAL OF COMMUNITY MEDICINE	3
INDIGENOUS PEOPLE AND NATURE: INSIGHTS FOR SOCIAL, ECOLOGICAL, AND TECHNOLOGICAL SUSTAINABILITY	3
ORIENTAL ANTHROPOLOGIST	3
CHILDREN AND YOUTH SERVICES REVIEW	2
CONTEMPORARY VOICE OF DALIT	2
ETHNOGRAPHIC RESEARCH IN THE SOCIAL SCIENCES	2

Sources: Authors' work; biblioshiny output

Figure 5. & Table 1. The bar chart displays the most relevant sources for research on the socioeconomic status and mental morbidity of Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups (PVTGs). The *Indian Journal of Medical Research* leads with the highest number of documents, followed by other important sources like the *Journal of Asian and African Studies* and *Clinical Epidemiology and Global Health*, each contributing significant research to the field. This suggests that these journals play a central role in the academic discourse around the challenges faced by PVTGs, particularly in the areas of health and socioeconomic issues

Table 2. Top 10 Sources' Local Impact

SOURCE	H_INDEX	G_INDEX	M_INDEX	TC	NP	PY_START
CHILDREN AND YOUTH SERVICES REVIEW	2	2	0.333	10	2	2020
CLINICAL EPIDEMIOLOGY AND GLOBAL HEALTH	2	2	0.4	7	3	2021
CONTEMPORARY VOICE OF DALIT	2	2	0.25	8	2	2018
FRONTIERS IN NUTRITION	2	2	0.333	48	2	2020
INDIAN JOURNAL OF MEDICAL RESEARCH	2	5	0.182	51	5	2015
INDIAN JOURNAL OF PUBLIC HEALTH	2	2	0.4	8	2	2021
JOURNAL OF ASIAN AND AFRICAN STUDIES	2	2	0.2	7	4	2016
ANNUAIRE ROUMAIN D'ANTHROPOLOGIE	1	1	0.077	1	1	2013
ASIAN JOURNAL OF INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH	1	1	0.25	1	1	2022
COMMUNITY DEVELOPMENT JOURNAL	1	1	0.5	1	1	2024

Sources: Authors' work; biblioshiny output

This table2 presents the local impact of various sources relevant to the research on the socioeconomic status and mental morbidity of Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups (PVTGs). Key metrics such as the h-index, g-index, m-index, total citations (TC), number of papers (NP), and the year of the first publication (PY_start) are provided for each source. Notably, *Indian Journal of Medical Research* stands out with 51 citations and a strong h-index of 2, reflecting its significant contribution to the field. Other influential sources like *Children and Youth Services Review* and *Clinical Epidemiology and Global Health* also play crucial roles in addressing the challenges faced by PVTGs, particularly in the domains of health and socioeconomic well-being. The table underscores the importance of these journals in advancing research on the intersection of poverty, health, and development for PVTGs

Table 3. Top 10 Authors' Local Impact

AUTHOR	H_INDEX	G_INDEX	M_INDEX	TC	NP	PY_START
DOWNS S	4	4	0.667	73	4	2020
FANZO J	4	4	0.667	73	4	2020
GHOSH-JERATH S	4	4	0.667	73	4	2020
KAPOOR R	4	4	0.667	73	4	2020
BHAT J	3	3	0.273	51	3	2015

RAO V	3	3	0.273	51	3	2015
SHARMA R	3	3	0.273	51	3	2015
SINGH A	3	4	0.5	68	4	2020
YADAV R	3	3	0.273	51	3	2015
BABU B	2	2	1	6	2	2024

Sources: Authors' work; biblioshiny output

This table 3 shows the local impact of various authors contributing to the research on the socioeconomic status and mental morbidity of Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups (PVTGs). It presents key metrics, including the h-index, g-index, m-index, total citations (TC), number of papers (NP), and the year of the first publication (PY_start). Authors like *Downs S*, *Fanzo J*, *Ghosh-Jerath S*, and *Kapoor R* are particularly influential, each having a high h-index of 4, which indicates a strong impact in the field with 73 citations and 4 papers each. Other authors such as *Bhat J* and *Rao V*, with an h-index of 3, also make notable contributions, reflecting the importance of their work on the health, education, and socio-economic conditions of PVTGs. The table highlights key figures who are advancing the research on PVTGs and their challenges

Table 4. Top 10 Most Relevant Affiliations

Affiliation	Articles
INDIAN COUNCIL OF MEDICAL RESEARCH (ICMR)	21
ICMR - REGIONAL MEDICAL RESEARCH CENTRE (RMRC), BHUBANESWAR	8
INDIRA GANDHI NATIONAL TRIBAL UNIVERSITY	5
KALINGA INSTITUTE OF INDUSTRIAL TECHNOLOGY (KIIT)	5
NATIONAL INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY ROURKELA	5
RUTGERS SCHOOL OF PUBLIC HEALTH	5
AGR UNIV	4
ICMR - NATIONAL INSTITUTE FOR RESEARCH IN TRIBAL HEALTH (NIRTH)	4
UNIVERSITY OF HYDERABAD	4
ALL INDIA INSTITUTE OF MEDICAL SCIENCES	3

Sources: Authors' work; biblioshiny output

This table 4 lists the most relevant affiliations contributing to the research on the socioeconomic status and mental morbidity of Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups (PVTGs). It highlights institutions such as the *Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR)*, which leads with 21 articles, followed by *ICMR - Regional Medical Research Centre (RMRC), Bhubaneswar* with 8 articles. Other notable contributors include *Indira Gandhi National Tribal University* and *Kalinga Institute of Industrial Technology* with 5 articles each. The table helps identify key research institutions driving the discourse on PVTGs' health and socio-economic challenges. By showing the affiliations, the author emphasizes the significant role of these institutions in generating knowledge about tribal health and development, particularly in India, and reveals which institutions are central to advancing research in this field. This data can guide future collaborations and highlight gaps in research that need attention. The author's purpose is to map the institutional landscape to understand where the most influential research is coming from and to identify potential gaps for future exploration

Figure 6. Country Scientific Production

Country Scientific Production

Sources: Authors' work; biblioshiny output

Table 5. Top 10 Country Scientific Production

Country	Freq
INDIA	144
USA	8
UK	2
CANADA	1
ETHIOPIA	1
MOROCCO	1
NETHERLANDS	1
ROMANIA	1
SAUDI ARABIA	1
TURKEY	1

Sources: Authors' work; biblioshiny output

Figure 6 & Table 5. The map and the table display the global distribution of scientific production related to the research on the socioeconomic status and mental morbidity of Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups (PVTGs). India is clearly the primary contributor, with 144 articles, reflected in the dark blue shading on the map. Other countries like the USA, UK, and several European nations contribute fewer articles, as indicated by the lighter shading. This table and figure underscore India's central role in producing knowledge on tribal health and development, suggesting that the majority of research on PVTGs is rooted in India. The author includes this data to highlight the geographical concentration of research, which can inform future collaborations and funding allocations for PVTGs research. The map also signals potential areas for growth in scientific contributions from other nations

Figure 7. Most Global Cited Documents

Sources: Authors' work; biblioshiny output

Figure 7. The chart and table display the most globally cited documents related to the socioeconomic status and mental morbidity of Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups (PVTGs). Notably, *Robledo S (2023)* stands out with the highest number of citations (38), followed by *Rao V (2015)* and *Ghosh-Jerath S (2021)*, each receiving significant attention. The table includes key details such as the total number of citations, citations per year, and normalized total citations. The author includes this data to highlight the most influential works in the field, which have contributed significantly to the global discourse on PVTGs' challenges. Understanding which papers have the most global impact is crucial for identifying the foundational research and guiding future studies, ensuring the effective addressing of key issues such as tribal health and education

Figure 8. Most Frequent Words

Sources: Authors' work; biblioshiny output

Figure 8. The chart and table present the most frequent keywords used in research related to the socioeconomic status and mental morbidity of Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups (PVTGs). The most frequently occurring terms include "PVTGs" (13 occurrences), "India" (12 occurrences), and "particularly vulnerable tribal groups" (9 occurrences). Other important terms such as "poverty,"

Figure 10. Trend Topics

Sources: Authors' work; biblioshiny output

Figure 10. The table and figure display the trend topics in research related to the socioeconomic status and mental morbidity of Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups (PVTGs). The figure shows the frequency of key terms over time, highlighting the increasing focus on topics such as "PVTGs" (13 occurrences), "India" (12 occurrences), and "particularly vulnerable tribal groups" (9 occurrences) in recent years. The table provides specific trends, with terms like "poverty" peaking in 2023, while "education" and "tribal" show steady attention in 2021–2024. The author includes this data to illustrate how the focus of research has evolved, with particular attention to the growing relevance of PVTGs and their associated issues, such as education, poverty, and health. This can guide future research by identifying key areas of focus, showing how these topics are being discussed over time, and helping to anticipate emerging research priorities

Figure 11. Collaboration Network

Sources: Authors' work; biblioshiny output

Figure 11. The figure and table display the collaboration network between countries, specifically highlighting the relationships between India, the United Kingdom, and the Netherlands. In the figure, India is positioned at the center, with links extending to both the United Kingdom and the Netherlands, suggesting collaborative research between these nations. The table provides metrics such as Betweenness, closeness, and PageRank for each country, all of which are identical for the three nations, indicating equal importance in the network. The author presents this data to illustrate international collaboration in research on Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups (PVTGs). By showing these connections, the author highlights how these countries are involved in the research ecosystem, which could be pivotal in shaping future collaborations and advancing the research on PVTGs' socio-economic and mental health challenges

Figure 12. Authors Network

Sources: Authors' work; biblioshiny output

The figure 12 show the network of authors involved in research on the socioeconomic status and mental morbidity of Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups (PVTGs). The network visualization groups authors into clusters based on their co-authorship relationships. For example, *Pati S* and *Bal M* are central nodes in the red cluster, indicating significant collaboration, while other clusters represent different author groups. The table provides key metrics such as Betweenness, closeness, and PageRank, where *Pati S* stands out with the highest Betweenness, indicating a pivotal role in connecting different parts of the network. The author presents this table to illustrate the key contributors and collaborative dynamics in the field. It helps identify the most influential authors and their connections, which is essential for understanding how research on PVTGs is evolving and which scholars are driving the discourse

Table 6. Most cited countries

Country	TC	Average Article Citations
INDIA	223	3.30
USA	43	14.30
ROMANIA	22	22.00
NETHERLANDS	12	12.00
CANADA	3	1.50
TURKEY	2	2.00
UGANDA	0	0.00

Sources: Authors' work; biblioshiny output

The table 6.Display the most cited countries in research related to the socioeconomic status and mental morbidity of Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups (PVTGs). India stands out with the highest total citations (223), followed by the USA (43) and Romania (22). The table also shows the average article citations for each country, where Romania has the highest average (22), followed by the USA (14.30), indicating that although India has the most citations, the impact of research from other countries like the USA and Romania is highly regarded. The author includes this data to highlight the global impact of PVTG-related research, showing the most influential countries in the field. This information is valuable for understanding where key research contributions are coming from and how they are being cited internationally

Figure 13. Publications & Citations

Sources: Authors' creation

The figure 13 display the top 20 publications in research related to the socioeconomic status and mental morbidity of Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups (PVTGs), comparing the total number of citations with the mean citations for each publication. BMC Oral Health has the highest number of

citations, followed by *Frontiers in Nutrition* and *Agricultural Systems*. The figure also shows the difference between the total number of citations (in green) and mean citations (in light green), indicating how widely each publication is cited on average. The author includes this data to highlight the most influential journals in the field of PVTG research. This information helps in understanding which publications have a broader academic impact, guiding future research directions and highlighting journals that focus on relevant themes like health, nutrition, and rural development

Figure 14. Collaboration network of authors

Sources: Authors' work; VOS-viewer output

The figure 14 shows a collaboration network of authors involved in the research on the socioeconomic status and mental morbidity of Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups (PVTGs). The nodes represent individual authors, and the edges between them show co-authorship relationships. Authors are grouped by color based on their co-authorship patterns, with distinct clusters indicating the collaborative groups. For example, the blue cluster includes authors like *Ghosh-Jerath*, *Suprana* and *Kapoor*, *Ridhima*, indicating strong collaboration within that group. The author includes this data to visualize the research collaboration landscape, highlighting which scholars and teams are most actively involved in PVTG research. Understanding these collaborations is essential for recognizing key contributors, potential research gaps, and areas for future collaboration

Conclusion

This study highlights the critical socio-economic and mental health challenges faced by Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups (PVTGs) in India. PVTGs are subjected to extreme poverty, limited access to healthcare and education, and geographic isolation, which significantly contribute to their marginalization (Banerjee, 2019; Das & Yadav, 2021). The fragmented research available points to a clear need for integrated approaches that simultaneously address these socioeconomic vulnerabilities

and the associated mental health morbidities, such as depression, anxiety, and PTSD, exacerbated by factors like social isolation and historical trauma (Rath & Sharma, 2022).

A key finding from this research is the gap in studies combining both socio-economic and mental health aspects of PVTGs, with few interdisciplinary efforts exploring how these dimensions intersect (Pati et al., 2019). The existing literature tends to address these issues in isolation, limiting the development of comprehensive interventions. The research underscores the importance of bringing together experts from various fields, such as sociology, psychology, and public health, to create holistic solutions for improving the well-being of these marginalized communities.

To improve the living conditions of PVTGs, the study stresses the need for multifaceted interventions that combine economic development, healthcare access, and mental health support. This approach will require enhanced policy-making that considers the socio-economic and mental health needs of PVTGs, and the creation of culturally sensitive mental health programs that respect tribal traditions (Vijayachari et al., 2024). Further research, particularly longitudinal and interdisciplinary studies, will be crucial in addressing the gaps in current understanding and shaping future policies and interventions for these vulnerable groups.

Implications of the study

This study provides valuable insights into the socioeconomic status (SES) and mental health of Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups (PVTGs) in India, highlighting critical gaps in existing research. The findings underscore the urgent need for targeted policy interventions to address both economic deprivation and mental health challenges faced by PVTGs. Policymakers must adopt a holistic approach, strengthening social welfare programs like the Tribal Sub-Plan (TSP) and Special Area Plans (SAP), while integrating traditional healing practices with modern mental health care to ensure culturally sensitive support (Das & Yadav, 2021; Vijayachari et al., 2024).

The study also calls for improvements in health infrastructure, especially in remote tribal areas, to make healthcare more accessible. Training healthcare providers to address the unique mental health needs of tribal populations is essential for offering comprehensive care (Thamminaina et al., 2020). For researchers, the study emphasizes the need for interdisciplinary approaches that explore the intersection of socioeconomic status and mental health, with a focus on longitudinal studies to assess the long-term effects of interventions (Banerjee, 2019).

For healthcare practitioners, culturally appropriate mental health care and community-based programs are vital to reducing stigma and ensuring access to mental health services. Mobile health clinics and telemedicine can bridge healthcare gaps in isolated regions (Thamminaina et al., 2020). Furthermore, empowering PVTGs through education, employment, and healthcare access is essential for improving their overall well-being. This research advocates for integrating cultural preservation into development programs, fostering resilience and identity, which can mitigate socioeconomic and mental health issues (Rath & Sharma, 2022). Overall, this study calls for comprehensive, integrated strategies to enhance the socio-economic and mental well-being of PVTGs.

Future Scope of Research

Future research on the socioeconomic status and mental health of Particularly Vulnerable Tribal Groups (PVTGs) should focus on interdisciplinary studies that explore the intersectionality between economic deprivation and mental health issues, combining perspectives from sociology, psychology, public health, and economics (Ghosh & Sharma, 2020). Longitudinal studies tracking the mental health outcomes of PVTGs over time, particularly in the context of interventions improving their socioeconomic conditions, are essential for understanding the long-term impact of these efforts. Additionally, research should emphasize culturally sensitive mental health interventions tailored to the unique needs of tribal communities, integrating traditional healing practices with modern mental health care approaches to enhance accessibility and acceptance (Vijayachari et al., 2024). The role of health policies and infrastructure in supporting PVTGs' well-being also warrants further exploration, with a focus on evaluating the effectiveness of governmental and non-governmental programs aimed at improving their healthcare and socio-economic status (Thamminaina et al., 2020). Emerging technologies, such as digital health platforms and telemedicine, offer promising solutions to address healthcare gaps in remote tribal areas, and their feasibility should be evaluated for supporting mental health and improving economic opportunities for PVTGs (Das & Yadav, 2021). Lastly, policy-oriented research is crucial to assess the impact of existing policies and welfare schemes, such as the Tribal Sub-Plan (TSP) and Special Area Plans (SAP), and to propose strategies for enhancing their implementation and effectiveness.

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